

Women As Victims And Heroines of The Nigerian Civil War: A Feminological Reading of Akachi Adimora-Ezeigbo's *Roses And Bullets*

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Abstract: The Civil war, which took place in Nigeria in 1967, cast devastating effects on the country's economy and the inhabitants therein. Worthy of tremendous mention are the Igbo people otherwise known as Biafra, occupying the East of the Southern part of Nigeria. During the war, young men are conscripted into the Biafran Army in order to match up their Nigerian counterpart, and young women, including the married ones are raped. Using feminism as a theoretical framework, this paper sees *Roses and Bullets* as a novel, which Ezeigbo uses to portray the plight of women during the Civil war. The paper unravels the bleak condition of women, making them victims of the war. The paper discovers that though women are used for sexual gratification during the war, the novelist empowers them with built-in vitality, which enables them to rise up against all odds to fight for their survival. Thus, their strive for survival make them heroines of the novel.

Keywords: Feminology, Victims, Heroines, Empower, Vindication

INTRODUCTION

Literature in its entirety is a product of the society; it draws its inspirations from the micro milieu, which serves as an indispensable parent to it. This is one of the reasons it tends to recreate it for the betterment of its inhabitants. Ngugi[1] has rightly given an inductive reasoning that literature does not develop in a vacuum; it is given impetus by the socio-cultural as well as economic and political factors that reign supreme in the macro milieu where it grows. Thus, writers have since begun to x-ray these factors that tend to influence the things that happen in the society. Consequent upon these assertions, Ezeigbo has been able to picture the experiences of the women during the civil war that ravaged Nigeria in 1967 in her handy novel, *Roses and Bullets*[2]. The experiences of these women as marshaled by Ezeigbo, are the principal concern of this paper.

Brief Theoretical Background

Feminism

Feminism is an ideology that promotes gender equality in society; it is a devotion to achieving equal rights for women by combating patriarchal and sexist enslavement that prevents them from realizing their full potential. In an attempt to define feminism, Gamble[3] observed:

[Feminism] is the belief that women, purely and simply because they are women, are treated inequitably within a society which is organized to prioritize male viewpoints and concerns. Within this patriarchal paradigm, women become everything men are not (or do not want to be seen to be): where men are regarded as strong, women are weak; where men are rational, they are emotional; where men are active, they are passive; and so on (vii).

Gamble further revealed that this rationale causes women to face negativity in all spheres and also denies them "equal access to the world of public concerns as well as of cultural representation" (vii). The aim of feminism is, therefore, to change this situation for the betterment of women and the progress of society. Bearing in mind the African context, Chukwuma[4] a feminist scholar and critic, proffered her own perception of feminism thus:

Feminism means a rejection of inferiority and a striving for recognition. It seeks to give the woman a sense of self as a worthy, effectual and contributing human being. Feminism is a reaction to such stereotypes of women which deny them a positive identity (ix)

According to Ezeigbo[5], feminism developed as a response to repressive and unfair laws and attitudes aimed at women [that have put them in] subordinate, dependent, and marginalized positions, permanently relegating them to the background... [Thus, feminism aims to] liberate and emancipate women worldwide from oppression, ignorance, poverty and self immolation” (1). A feminist, desire “is to articulate a self hen, is one whose consciousness about women’s identity both as inherited cultural fact and as a process of social construction [and to] protest against the available [negative perceptions] of female becoming” [6]. An offshoot of the Women’s Liberation Movement in Europe and America, feminism dates back to the 18th century and the aftermath of the Reformation. It was a period which witnessed a change in social values during which men began to seek personal and political freedom.

Being fully aware of the parochial roles given to them in the society, women began to crave a share of this new liberty. In Europe, Mary Wollstonecraft in her feminist tract, “Vindications of the Rights of Women”, called for consciousness raising in women through education (Freeman, 13). This message resonated with many including John Stuart Mill who showed his support in an essay entitled “The Subjugation of Women”. Other famous intellectuals and organizations added their voices, resulting in the formation of the European feminist movement. Changes in social values and social structure (following the American Revolution) have been highlighted as the two social processes that contributed to the emergence of equalitarian values in the United States.

Victimization of Women in *Roses and Bullets*

The multi-syllabic word “victimization” is morphologically derived from the disyllabic word ‘victim’ that is literally defined by the *Cambridge Advanced Learner’s Dictionary*[7] as “someone or something, which has been hurt, demerged, or killed or has suffered, either because of the actions or something else, or because of illness or chance.” However, applying the above semantic implication to our tenor of discourse, the following puzzling, thought-provoking questions become unavoidably and inevitably pertinent; viz, who is being hurt? Who is suffering? And who is being killed? Of course the apt answers supplied these seeming open-ended questions shall in no mean way liven our analytical gusto.

Drifting our illuminating search light into the novel, it becomes apparent that the perceived instances of victimization in the novel start right in the house of Dr. Uba Ezeuko, who is a medical doctor, professionally speaking. When sternly interrogated by his son, Nwakire for what he has done to Ginika, Uba in a bit to supply hypnotizing answers to his question reminisces into the past; he recounts his sister’s ordeal, as the narrator puts it:

...I came home after my studies to discover that my sister had been impregnated by her teacher in primary five and had died as he tried to assist her in aborting the pregnancy. It was the most shattering experience of my life at the time. You can imagine how I felt; she had died just before my ship docked at the Port Harcourt harbor. So the first social event I witnessed on my return from abroad was my sister’s funeral. It was then I swore that such a thing would not happen to me again, and that and that I will take adequate steps to protect my female children or relations. This happened before I married your mother” (157).

Ginika attends a dance party with her friends and returns late to the house. Although the party did not start at the arranged time, couple with the fact that the bicycle they rode on got punctured, his father refuses to hear her out. He takes her to his room, gets her undressed and runs a check on her virginity. Ginika becomes extremely exasperated and devastated. She detest the stereotype that she is not able to take care of herself, making his obstinate father keep putting her to scorn and at most, invades her privacy.

Implicit in the above quote lifted from the text, is the demeaning fact that Uba is directly transferring his aggression to Ginika. Thus, Ginika becomes the victim of what happened to his sister in time past. Uba victimizes Ginika in a fit under the pretext of offering her the necessary protection. This action from Uba creates a sharp situational irony in the novel. According to Perrine:

The discrepancy in an irony of situation is between appearance and reality, or between what expectation and fulfillment, or between what is and what would seem appropriate [8].

In a careful attempt to demystify the above point, Worgu adduced that:

This is therefore to imply that two main levels of cognition operating within any given ironical situation present themselves: the level of ‘illusion’ and the level of ‘reality’ (although illusion is the illusive way in which the ‘victim’ of the irony perceives the world (where there is a victim), or the way the writer literally or ostensibly presents life (67).

Engaging situational irony as illustrated by Worgu above, we can establish the fact that the victim of circumstance, which had befallen Uba’s sister and whose occurrence Uba has sworn briskly to fight tooth and nail, resurfaces in a

different way. In order to protect Ginika from his sister's fate, Uba watches her closely and worse still, exerts his full force on her emotional well-being. He dictates what she does and tends to oversee all that concerns her, oblivious of the universal truth that every child who has attained his/her age of discretion needs some kind of privacy. Therefore, by pressing so hard at her, with such ignoble display of fatherly concern or protection, he has doused her moral and emotional rectitude, thereby, inadvertently making her a scapegoat of the experience of his sister, hence victimization. The circumstance he has been trying so hard to avert resurfaces in the act of repulsion. So, Uba's actions are no repellent, they only aggravate the situation.

In a different scenario, Ginika the heroine is victimized by his father. Some instances of victimization in the novel come into play in the form of what is called transfer of aggression. Frantz Fanon asserts that the case of neocolonialism is just a sheer transfer of aggression from the elite. This aggression germinated from what the white-men did to Africa, and since they could not avenge it, they decided to unleash this emotional turpitude on their brothers. This act is a type of defense mechanism which Kinanee Jumbo called "displacement."

Back to the novel, we see Uba directly transferring aggression on Ginika who is head over heels ignorant and innocent of her brother's action. Nwakire, noticing his manhood being cut in the web of boredom, decides in the secrecy of his heart, (which Ngugi in his *Devil on the Cross* describes as a 'dense forest') to join the Biafran Army, and leaves for it without seeking his father's consent. His father frowns at the stark enormity of his ineffable decision when he learns about it in the letter he is written by his son, as the narrator puts it:

"You will read it? You are both the same, are you not" he sneered. "Tell me, was he right to treat me, his father, with such disrespect? Such callousness how can one understand it? I do not know what I did to you two to deserve the way you treat me. Both of you have been time and time again. I do my best for you, but you hardly show appreciation. I am sure you knew he was going to do this, did you not? He could not have done it without telling you, could he? (111)

From the above show of emotional flow, we will believe that the brusque words meant for Nwakire have been directly transferred to Ginika, thereby victimizing her for her brother's action that she initially knows nothing about. When Eloka and Ginika become husband and wife, they enact a long-standing memorandum of understanding. The primary thing in this agreement is that they will hold their peace until after the war, and thereafter start to procreate when they must have attained their expected height in their educational pursuit. However, when Eloka leaves the house for his duties in the Biafran Army, his mother, Mrs. Odunze starts emitting heat on Ginika, nagging at her at every given time for refusing to give birth to a child. In this scenario, Ginika becomes a victim of what she and Eloka have planned. It will be pertinent to state here that, it is the nagging from Mrs. Odunze that catapults Ginika to her ill fate, as she (Ginika) decides to go with Janet to a dance party in a bit to escape from this emotional trauma caused her by her mother-in-law, as the narrator puts it:

Ginika stood transfixed for a full minute before she began to scrub the floor of the kitchen. She boiled up inside of her. With her hands shaking and her eyes flashing, she spat "I' not a slave or prisoner in this house and no one can make me one. I'm going to the dance with Janet. And no one can stop me". She missed loudly and flung the scrubbing brush away from her and it hit the wall with a thud. (369).

When the war becomes so intense, women automatically become victims, as the Biafran soldiers compel them into immoral sex. They rape women mercilessly, thereby trivializing their feelings. Soldiers see women as just an object of sexual gratification. They see them as an object, which can be used and thereafter discarded. Women suffer a great deal of victimization in the tenacious hands of these recalcitrant soldiers. The confession of a soldier confirms these assertions: "He remembered captain Akudo who was addicted to sex with teenagers. To him women were beautiful object to be ravished and thrown away. "They taste differently when they are quite young" (489.)

Although many women are being raped including autie chito, when she was still single, the study shall steady it analogy on the cases of Ginika and Boma. Ginika is superbly raped twice in the course of the war. The first incident culminates in her misfortune. Having been severely harangued by her mother-in-law, she sees the chance party as an egregious escapism. At the party, she is drugged and raped by a Biafran Army Lieutenant whose hormone testosterone secretes the hyperactive semen that further deteriorates her trauma. Thus, she becomes a victim of the war.

Let us also establish the point that someone must not die for him/her to be seen as a victim. Recalled that this assertion is in line with the definition of victim provided at the beginning of this critical vignette and in tandem with what John Pepper Clark Bekederemo said in his "The Casualties". He opines that casualties are not only those who are dead wounded or those who started a fire and cannot quench it but the casualties are the scapegoats, the innocents who had no

say in the matter, and they are victims of the fire. They are also the ones that survive the ragging war, and reside in the devastated shell of its aftermath.

The second incident that befalls Ginika comes in the end of the war when she is completely loved by Sergeant Sule who lavishes her with many costly surprised gifts. In order to douse his sexual passes, Ginika tells him that it will only result in an abomination in her family if she should give in to the sexual passes of an uncircumcised man. Glutted with the feelings of love, Sergeant Sule indulges in a circumcision rite for him to be able to fit into Ginika's purported traditional demands, and dies from the infection of the wound rendered him by the circumcision blade. The sudden death of Sergeant Sule spurs another Sergeant to arrest and forcefully rapes Ginika, thereby, shifting the blame of the lurid and unspeakable action of the late Sergeant on her very head, hence, victimization.

In the case of Boma, she is raped by a Biafran Soldier whose high sperm count gets her pregnant. She is only helped by the compassionate captain Eloka, who takes her in with no strings attached.

Women as Heroines in *Roses and Bullets*

Heroines according to the *Cambridge Advanced Learner's* mean "a person who is admired for having done something very brave or having achieved something great". When talking about heroines in a piece of literary text, some scholars think that it is only someone or persons that fight in a war and perhaps becomes victorious that should be referred to as being the heroes or heroines. This stereotype is not the only deed with which a hero or heroine should be known. It will puzzle us to know that although Ginika, Njide and of course Eunice did not go to war, they are the heroines of the novel. Their brave deeds qualify them as such.

During war, it is only cowards that are frightened by bullets or the thought of handling guns. These are the likes of Osundu and Michael. However, when someone is unperturbed by the ceaseless sounds of war guns then we say such person is brave.. Since the eruption of the war, many young men have been conscripted into the Biafran Army and the women left to tend the children. But some of the brave girls look for a way to contribute to the victory of the Biafran soldiers, deeply engrossed with the optimistic thought that things will be better after the ravaging war which the 'vandals' have waged against Biafra.

At the time when the war becomes so intense, schools are closed and students/pupils are asked to go home to their parents or in loco parentis so that they will not be alienated or estranged from them when the 'vandals' attack. People become displaced and lousiness assumes an epileptic, nondescript outlook. Ginika leaves school and is now living with auntie Chito in Enugu. It will be note worthy to state here that it is while living with her auntie in Enugu that the heroic thought of doing something to help those combating in the war actually begins. At her auntie's house, she helps in running little errands, house chores and at best prepares 'snacks' for the soldiers who are fighting the war. She relishes or takes delight in cooking, as this is her own contribution in winning the war, as the narrator puts it:

Encouraged, Ginika persisted, "I love it out here. I want to remain in Enugu. Helping to prepare delectable snacks for our soldiers at the Nsukka front is my own win-the-war effort. Auntie, can't you and Uncle Ray persuade Papa to allow me to stay here?" (19).

At Mbano, Ginika is trained as a special constable. During the time her training spans, she is placed ahead of the rest would-be constables because of her studious nature. Her elevation to the position of the best trainee constable, which ends her little enmity from fellows, accentuates her heroic and superlative nature. Were it not for this special training, the Nigerian soldier that seized her when Sergeant Sule died could have been able to rape her all alone. He only employed the assistance of other soldiers when Ginika has applied her skill on him. It will also be useful to adduce that the several severe 'tantrums' she unleashes at his father when she is being forcefully taken to Mbano, is a remarkable heroic performance.

The whole novel is predicated on the series of plays they stage at strategic military campus in which she (Ginika) plays the mermaid. Mermaid in their play is used like what is called *Deus ex machina* (god of the machine). Gotthardt defined it as "a character which enters a story to bring relief or help, but who has not had an integral or important role to play in the plot". (16). Recalled that the apparition of Hamlet that appears at the grave had to reveal the mystery behind his death to prince Hamlet, is a *Deus ex machine*. In their play, the mermaid is to pass judgment on the war in favour of Biafran soldiers. It is schematized in such a way that the play foregrounds a fictitious law court where the case between Nigeria and the indigenous people of Biafra is legally judged in favour of the Biafrans. By playing this role, she becomes a superb heroine in the entire novel. In addition, by offering voluntarily to work at the war front with The Red Cross Society, Njide becomes a hero. Eunice also shows some level of heroic deed by cooking for the soldiers at the war front. At best, these characters work tooth and nail to see to the victory of the soldiers of the indigenous people of Biafra.

Of course, this critical vignette will remain incomplete if we mention the heroines in the novel without at least giving a modicum of credit to auntie Chito. Auntie Chito is portrayed as the hub of the heroic awareness that engulfs Ginika. She serves as a counselor, guide and in its enormity, a confidante who laces and bedecks the central character with all the information about how to live a life. She always motivates and supports Ginika, in fact, she makes her (Ginika) remains undeterred in her decision. Even when Ginika commits an abomination, she consents to the plea to help her talk to Eloka (Ginika's Husband). For acting as Ginika's refuge, she is therefore a semi-heroine. Her advisory role is evident in the quote below:

Her aunt pressed her to her bosom, held for a while without uttering a word. "Ozuone, it is enough. Hold your head up and go with ebb and flow of the tides, or they will drown you. God knows you might find life better in Mbano when you get there. Remember what I told you yesterday, always be set on being whoever you want to be. It sounds a great ideal to serve your country in any other way. Go for it, dearie!" (28).

Survival Strategies of the Women in *Roses and Bullets*

Generally, survival is the adjectival derivative of the verb, 'survive' which the *Cambridge Advanced Learner's Dictionary* defines Survival as "to continue to live or exist, especially after coming close to dying or being destroyed or after being in a difficult or threatening situation" (1310). No matter how threatening the vicissitudes of life may seem, all living things must strive stoutly for their survival. Biologically speaking, survival is the essence to all living organisms. For instance, the reptile Chameleon is widely known for its inconsistent colours to suit his environment. This type of change is biologically called coloration. It changes colour to be able to catch its prey for food. It also changes colour when it notices danger in its environment. The danger could be caused by its predator. So in order to survive this, it changes colour. For instance, if it runs into green grasses, it changes its colour to green to be invisible to its predator. Thus, this action is what is generally known as survival strategy.

Returning our full gaze to the novel we discover that most of the girls flock to the soldiers for survival. Though this act may be misunderstood for harlotry, but the underlying motive behind this seeming uncanny display, is to scout for life supporting essence which is unmistakably food for survival. Janet a refugee, who is also employed as a worker in the refugee camp, indulges in what is called calculated prostitution in order to survive in the war. Recalled that Adisa in Iyayi's violence plunges into this in order to save her husband who is not able to pay his hospital bills. Queen also indulges in prostitution in order to win contracts for the survival of the family in the same novel. With the listed paradigm, we sternly justify the point that it is the sheer thought of surviving the claws of hunger inherent in the war that makes Janet keep both an army officer and an air force officer. The proceed she realizes from this calculated prostitution, both cash and kind, added to the one she gathers from the refugee camp, help her to maintain status quo.

When a mother hen forages for food with its chick, it covers them completely as soon as it sights the hawk. At best, the owners of the hen would rob the chicks and the mother hen with clayish ink so that the hawk would mistake them for a kind of bird, thereby allowing them freedom. This is what is called survival strategy. When Ginika's family both his cousin, Udo's family, and his aunt's family are famished. Ginika maps out a survival strategy. She decides to follow the rest traders to buy food stuff at Attack Market otherwise called "afia attack." The narrator calls this "trading behind the enemy line". Behind the enemy line is the place where the vandals reside and are ready to shoot at sight. The unique fact about this market is that things are relatively cheap, and many commodities are easily located. She takes this seeming foolhardy risk because of the ravaging hunger in the house. She goes to the market alongside other traders, Eunice inclusive, but unfortunately, the vandals shoot at them. Eunice loses her life, while the rest traders including Ginika jettison their goods to free themselves from their seeming incarceration as they take to their heels.

At the termination of the war, Ginika Marshalls another survival strategy. Since the end of the war marks the discarding of the Biafran currency, she decides to convert the bags of beans Udo carried from the refugee camp into beans pudding otherwise called *Akara*. This becomes her new survival strategy. She makes cool Nigeria currency form this and life becomes interesting for her and her aunt.

It is an undeniable fact that when groups of fishes are being entangled or double-crossed with fishing nets, they stubbornly splish for survival. Even in the Bible when Jacob and his household are driven by hunger, they move compromisingly to Egypt for food. That was the same case with girls in the novel. When the war (which was invariably the fishing net in the above example) is about to famish them to death, they flock to the soldiers. Seeing their hungry nature, the soldiers begin to take undue advantage of them as the narrator puts it:

Some of the other officers though war has a way of compromising morals and so they didn't think the girls were doing something outrageous or immoral. They argued that the fear of death, the ever present threat to life in a war situation makes people reckless and

increases their sex drive. They argued too that people in war time are more likely to fall in and out of love easily and would have sex with any available partner. (477-478).

CONCLUSION

To conclude this essay, it is pertinent to include here the dictum, 'Necessity leads to invention.' It was necessary for the girls to eat to survive the claws of hunger. And since they knew that 'nothing goes for nothing' they had to use what they had to get what they wanted. So, this calculated act of improvisation becomes their survival strategy. Thus, the barbarity of both the Nigerian soldiers and Biafran soldiers harden the women so that they become heroines of the war, recounting from their win-the-war efforts and survival strategies.

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